

The Islamic State: A Clash within the Muslim Civilization for the New Caliphate

DOI: [10.1080/1057610X.2015.1100010](https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2015.1100010)

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Journal: [Studies in Conflict & Terrorism](#) Vol. 39-2 (February 2016)
1057-610X (Print), 1521-0731 (Online)

Published online: 9 November 2015

Download Current Citation: [RIS](#) [BibTex](#)

Abstract

This study analyzes the political reasons that allowed the Islamic State to expand successfully in Syria and Iraq, by enabling to 'franchise' worldwide, and the role of the regional governments in this issue. The essay provides a different explanation from the classic approach of the "clash of civilizations" theorized by Samuel P. Huntington, ascribing responsibility for the growth and expansion of the Islamic State to the complex framework of geopolitical alliances within the Muslim civilization and the Arab world. The paper highlights the attempt by Turkey to establish itself as a regional power and guidance of the Islamic world, by resurrecting the Caliphate, and, based on this, explains the contrast with the Islamic State, which goal is the foundation of a globalized Caliphate. The plans of the Turkish President Erdoğan for a Great Turkey, allied with Egypt, have foundered with the coup that ousted the Muslim Brotherhood from power. The study relates the connection of Ankara with the Kurds, regarding the management of the crisis in Syria and Iraq, and the Turkish liaison with regional powers (Iran, Egypt, Saudi Arabia and Israel) and other powers (Russia, Cina and USA).

You can download the article published online by Taylor & Francis Group in *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* on 09/11/2015, available online: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1057610X.2015.1100010>.

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